

Unravelling the Dynamics of Landslide Occurrences and Joint Plane Influences in the Lesser-Himalayan Terrain: A Case Study of Ramban-Gul Road

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ABSTRACT

In the context of research focused on the structurally anisotropic Sub-Himalayan regions, the frequency of landslides or slope failures exhibits significant variation from one location to another. This variability can be attributed to underlying structural features and neotectonic activities. A notable case study of Ramban-Gul Road lies within the Jammu Himalaya, where a series of impactful landslides have occurred in recent times. Noteworthy among these are ongoing events like the Khuni Nala Rock-fall, Dhamkund Landslide, and Kora Pani Landslide. The manifestation of landslide activities in the Jammu Himalaya, including processes like falling, toppling, slumping, debris flow, debris slide, and land creeping, predominantly occurs in regions characterized by Low-hills exhibiting moderate to steep slopes. Within this geographical setting, the occurrence of landslide events is influenced by a range of intrinsic and extrinsic factors. These factors encompass geomorphological attributes, morphometric characteristics, lithological composition, structural arrangements, tectonic dynamics, and joint conditions. The interaction of these factors operates in conjunction with slope gradients, a relationship highlighted by previous studies. In the examined transect of the study area, numerous instances of landslides have been observed. However, a majority of these occurrences have undergone treatment interventions. Curiously, the treatment approach employed across the area remains relatively uniform, regardless of the diverse lithological compositions and varying overburden loads present in different areas. As part of this research endeavour, a subset of nine particularly unstable slopes from the identified landslide sites was selected for in-depth analysis. This analysis seeks to elucidate the specific role played by joint planes in the initiation and progression of these landslides. The ensuing article presents a comprehensive exploration of the details pertaining to these selected landslides, shedding light on the intricate relationships between joint plane characteristics and landslide occurrences.

Key words: Landslide, Jammu Himalayas, Slope Stability, NSMR, RMR

INTRODUCTION

In the realm of engineering projects, the maintenance of any endeavour is intricately tied to the geotechnical understanding of the project site and the surrounding geological and morphological conditions. However, in mountainous terrains, both geological and morphological conditions are subject to substantial variations, which can exert direct or indirect influences on the success of a project. This situation becomes particularly complex in the context of hydroelectric projects (HEPs), as evidenced by prior research (Krishnaswami and Singh 2005), owing to the presence of significant water bodies. Among the

critical components demanding meticulous examination within a HEP framework, the Catchment Area Treatment (CAT) plan takes a prominent position. The formulation of CAT plans hinges on two fundamental data inputs, updated periodically: water (both surface and groundwater) and the sediment load carried into the reservoir. This sediment load bears a direct impact on the storage capacity of the reservoir, consequently amplifying the construction, production, and maintenance costs associated with HEPs.

This sediment load, often referred to as silt load, is intrinsically linked to erosion processes upstream, which in turn are influenced by the properties of the upper soil cover. Specifically, areas with highly jointed rock strata or regions characterized by low values of geotechnical classifications tend to be particularly susceptible. Thus, conducting exhaustive geotechnical investigations assumes paramount importance. To address this, comprehensive geotechnical surveys were systematically

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conducted within the Chenab River basin, focusing on selected regions. The field data gleaned from these geotechnical studies play a pivotal role in not only orienting the understanding of unstable slopes but also in delineating their geometric characteristics. Furthermore, these surveys offer a means to identify areas of heightened erosion risk through the identification of low geotechnical classification values. Through this holistic approach, this research endeavours to contribute to the enhancement of sustainable maintenance strategies for engineering projects, especially within the context of mountainous terrains and hydroelectric projects.

METHODOLOGY

The classification of rocks based on geotechnical properties has undergone continuous refinement by pioneering researchers since its inception (Terzaghi 1946; Løset 1992). These classifications have evolved over time to account for various geological and geomorphological conditions. Examples include Rock Structure Rating (RSR; Wickham et al. 1972), later renamed Rock Mass Rating (RMR; Bieniaswki 1973, 1976), Q-system (Barton et al., 1974), and Laubscher's Classification (1977). These systems have seen further amendments with the incorporation of numerous parameters, aiming for more precise characterization of ground conditions and more accurate load assessments. Examples of these modified systems include Mining Basic RMR (MBR; Kandorski et al., 1983), RMR_b (Basic RMR; Bieniawski 1989), Modified RMR (MRMR; Unal 1990), Rock Mass Index (RMI; Palmstrom 1982, 1995), and Rock Engineering Systems (RES; Mazzoccola and Hudson, 1996). Researchers have also identified limitations inherent in these geotechnical classifications (Palmstrom and Broch 2006).

One of these prominent classifications, RMR (Bieniaswki, 1989), served as the basis for Romana's (1993) proposal of a slope classification system, known as Slope Mass Rating (SMR). This classification system assesses slope stability and has found widespread application globally, including in India (Prakash et al. 2003). The SMR technique has been site-specific and has undergone refinements based on rock conditions (Moon et al. 2001) and topography.

The adoption of these classification systems necessitates the consideration of specific parameters, for which data collection techniques have evolved alongside advancing

instrumentation. These parameters encompass rock strength (Brown 1981; Hoek 2012), rock quality designation (RQD; Deere and Deere 1988), joint orientation and spacing conditions (Palmström, 1995; Laubscher, 1984), water saturation (Hoek, 2012), weathering (Williamson and Kuhn, 1988), and roughness (Stimpson, 1982).

In the context of this study, base maps were primarily generated using satellite images and digital elevation models (DEMs). Where accessible, outcrops were surveyed using total station equipment and processed using AutoCAD. The collected dataset also incorporated information about landslide occurrences, their locations, and frequency. This study encompasses an examination of the impact of these landslides on local lifestyles and property. Data collection occurred through predefined data sheets (Appendix I), including details about the types of sliding, the primary factors (both direct and indirect) contributing to sliding at the sites, and geological information collection.

Sample Preparation and Data Collection

The geotechnical analyses, the bedrock rests upon the meticulous gathering and assessment of field data. This process of geotechnical data collection and subsequent evaluation holds paramount importance in the domain of rock mechanical analysis. Within the context of this current research, the acquisition of data was meticulously executed through the utilization of diverse field datasheets. These data sheets were thoughtfully designed to capture the intricate rock joint parameters as prescribed by the Rock Mass Rating (RMR) system introduced by Bieniaswki in 1989, as well as the slope parameters stipulated by the Slope Mass Rating (SMR) system proposed by Romana in 1993. In addition to the systematic data collection from the field, acute attention was directed toward recording the nuances of outcrop sketches and overarching geomorphic conditions encountered during the field survey. These on-site sketches and observations contribute critical contextual insights to the dataset, enhancing the richness and precision of the gathered information. Subsequent to the successful completion of the field data collection phase, the research journey advanced into the laboratory domain. Herein, a dual trajectory commenced, encompassing the processing and examination of both collected field data and rock samples. This multi-faceted endeavour aimed to address a diverse spectrum of parameters essential for comprehensive analysis and insightful interpretation.

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Discontinuity Data

Within the scope of this research paper, comprehensive data pertaining to joint characteristics and discontinuities was gathered. The terminological breadth of “discontinuity” encompasses an array of features such as minor and major joints, bedding planes or foliation, shear zones, faults, and other surfaces of vulnerability (Matula and Holzer 1978; Hoek et al., 1992; Milne et al., 1992). The data collected encompasses parameters of continuity, aperture, and frequency, alongside their respective orientations. Traditional methodologies designate the orientation of bedding planes as joints, denoting them as ‘S0’. Notably, well-defined structures penetrating rock strata are termed master joints (Bell, 1992), while minor joints are denoted as “J1, J2, ..., Jn” in sequential order based on a clockwise joint strike direction (Nawani 2011).

The investigation area exhibited four sets of joints, primarily consisting of cross-joint sets, with discernible longitudinal joint sets as well. To quantitatively analyze these features, a total of 39 slopes were examined for joint orientation and spacing. Each slope location entailed around 60-70 joint orientation measurements within a 5×5m² area, contingent upon the available free surface. The joint data was categorized according to four joint properties: joint orientation (kinematic analysis), joint frequency (volumetric analysis), joint continuity (spacing measurements), and joint aperture (observations on separation and infilling). These properties are presented and discussed sequentially.

The collected slope and discontinuity data were subjected to kinematic analysis by projecting dip and strike data of discontinuities and slope surfaces onto stereographic diagrams. While the primary focus of this study is the wedge failure analysis of slopes, the procured discontinuity data can also be qualitatively employed to assess various aspects of discontinuities pertinent to slope stability, in accordance with Barton and Choubey (1977). The kinematic analysis furnishes insights into daylighting, dip-slope interactions, and wedge-friction behaviour (Hoek and Bray, 1981), thereby offering crucial indicators of slope stability. Given the impracticality of obtaining Rock Quality Designation (RQD) data via borehole cores for the extensive Chenab river basin, an alternate approach of joint volumetric analysis was adopted. This method necessitates joint frequency data within a specific volume; consequently, the

study involved manual counting of joints along a 2-meter stretch on different exposed rock surfaces.

Moreover, the present research included the measurement of spacings between parallel surfaces, following the approach proposed by Bieniawski (1989). The overall condition of a discontinuity is predicted by joint condition factors, determined by the frictional characteristics of block faces and the relative scale effect (Palmstrøm 1995). This condition is influenced by factors such as length, roughness, separation, weathering of the wall rock or planes of weakness, and infilling material. These factors collectively reflect the extent and impact of a discontinuity, recorded numerically through tabular representations and field-prepared block diagrams and sketches. Interestingly, a prevailing trend of joint separation was observed in the study area, where smaller separations tended to enhance rock stability. This phenomenon arises from increased interlocking of asperities on the rock walls, bolstered by contributions from both filling material and the rock itself (Barton et al., 1974). Given the tectonic activity within the Himalayan terrain, the roughness of discontinuity surfaces provides insights into terrain stability. Furthermore, observations spanned a spectrum from fresh rock exposures to decomposed rock material, with different weathering states (as noted by Lama and Vatukuri 1978) further influencing slope instability conditions.

Rock Strength Data

It is widely recognized by global researchers that the surface strength of intact rock plays a crucial role in the realm of deformation, as indicated in the works of various authors (Coates, 1964; Piteau, 1973; Bieniawski, 1989; Palmstrøm, 1995). Given the diverse range of rock formations present in the study area, a comprehensive approach was undertaken. Approximately 10 to 15 samples from each litho-type were meticulously collected during field expeditions. Subsequent laboratory compression tests were conducted in accordance with the recommendations of the International Society for Rock Mechanics (ISRM 1978). The scarcity of extremely robust rocks within the study area led to the predominance of moderate rock strength classifications. Due to the expansive nature of the study region, it was neither feasible nor practical to assess compressive strength at every location. Consequently, the implementation of the Schmidt Hammer (also known as the Schmidt Impact Hammer, Sclerometer, or Swiss Hammer) facilitated a quantitative extrapolation

of strength values, a methodology advocated by Brown (1990). The Original Schmidt Hammer - Type L (S/N 7281), calibrated in February 2012, was utilized during fieldwork. This cost-effective, expeditious, and reliable technique (Haramy and De Marco 1985) generates R-values (dimensionless values) with each impact. Approximately 20-30 R-values were gauged on an approximately 2x2m² surface at exposure sites, with the subsequent average serving as the basis for further calculations. Following this, an empirical relationship was established between the measured R-values and the Load Bearing Capacity for distinct rock types. This relationship function was subsequently applied to each location to derive compressive strength, a pivotal parameter in the computation of the Rock Mass Rating (RMR; Bieniawski 1989).

The rock specimens procured from the field underwent trimming at the geotechnical laboratory housed within the Department of Geology at the University of Delhi. These specimens were trimmed to dimensions of 150x20x20mm³. Post-elimination of flawed and cracked samples, a total of 116 samples were subjected to load bearing capacity analysis. The "Micro Controller Based Compression Testing Machine," designed by Aimil Industries Limited, Delhi, and calibrated in May 2012, played a vital role in these assessments. This testing machine boasts a load capacity spanning 50kN to 5000kN, with capabilities for peak stress calculations. The machine provided the maximum load at the point of failure (P), and subsequently, the Uniaxial Compressive Strength (UCS) of each sample was computed using a designated equation. The average value of UCS for each rock type was then determined and applied in subsequent analyses.

UCS= Maximum Load at Failure / Cross-sectional Area of the Sample

Further, the data was analyzed statistically to determine the variability in the results. The rock samples were collected and tested from different lithological formations to evaluate the correlations between the UCS or Compression test results and the corresponding Schmidt Hammer test results.

Water Condition Data

The infiltration of water through fractures and discontinuities within rock formations yields a consequential reduction in

the effective normal stress along these joints, thereby diminishing the overall stability of rock slopes. Given the absence of comprehensive groundwater data within the study area, our approach involved visual assessments of seepage conditions, classified into categories such as completely dry, damp, wet, dripping, and flowing. These conditions were evaluated based on a rating system advocated by Bieniawski (1989). To ensure the accurate collection of seepage data from discontinuities, we adhered to the guidelines outlined by Barton et al. (1974).

Nonetheless, it is noteworthy that the development of seepage forces along joints, coupled with instances of rockfall from mountain cliffs as documented in various regions, often exhibits correlations with elevated water pressure and peak rainfall events. Consequently, within the study area, subsurface water may exacerbate instability through various mechanisms. Specifically, these mechanisms encompass but are not limited to, the following four pathways. Furthermore, it's important to acknowledge that water's presence can induce softening and potential outwash, particularly in the context of softer fillings such as clay stones, phyllites, and rocks characterized by a high mica content.

DATA PROCESSING

The Himalayan region is subjected to significant tectonic stress, which in turn generates varying degrees of deformation in the rocks within the designated geotechnical mapping area. This deformation data is crucial and is captured in terms of discontinuities, which serve as fundamental units for geotechnical assessment. Discontinuities mark shifts in the engineering properties of the surrounding rock mass. Therefore, meticulous records of discontinuity orientations and frequencies have been both documented and graphically plotted onto the base map.

For each landslide area, typically characterized by uniform lithological conditions and identified by a specific location number, a comprehensive base map has been meticulously produced using total station survey methods, covering the entire span from crown to toe. These base maps have been enriched with pertinent geological and geotechnical field data as aforementioned.

The accumulated dataset is subjected to analysis through diverse statistical and Geographic Information System (GIS)

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software tools, enabling the assessment of the New Slope Mass Rating (NSMR; Singh et al. 2013) across the study area. The subsequent sections expound upon the processes involved in software utilization and the resultant analyses.

Kinematic Analysis

The kinematic analysis was facilitated through the utilization of the DIPANALYST software, a readily available resource as highlighted by Admassu and Shakoor (2013). This software mandates specific data inputs, including strata orientation, slope face orientation, and the friction angle of the slide. By processing this information, the software generates results in the form of a failure index. This quantitative approach to kinematic analysis offers insights into the nature of failure (be it plane, toppling, or wedge) by generating corresponding failure indices. In the analysis of each landslide location, more than 100 joint surface orientations (dip angle and direction) were combined with the overarching slope orientation gleaned from slope and aspect maps. Additionally, friction angle values were integrated into the analysis. The interrelation between the friction angle, slope angle, slope azimuth, and failure indices were also scrutinized, with distinct plots aiding in the visualization of these relationships.

Rock Mass Condition Analysis

The Basic Rock Mass Rating (RMR_b) system, introduced by Bieniawski (1989) and also embraced by the South African Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, is employed to numerically characterize the rock condition within the study area. In the current investigation, five distinct parameters were systematically gathered and their correlation with the RMR_b system, as outlined by Bieniawski (1989), is explored.

$$RMR_b = P1 + P2 + P3 + P4 + P5 - P6$$

Where, P1 is rock strength rating parameter; P2 is rock quality designation rating parameter; P3 is discontinuity spacing rating parameter; P4 is discontinuity condition (sum of five joint parameters, i.e. joint persistence, joint separation, infilling, joint roughness and joint weathering condition rating) rating parameter; P5 is groundwater condition rating parameter; and P6 (introduced by Wickham et al. 1972) is the effect of discontinuity orientation which is a relation between the orientation of

dip strata and the orientation of construction. But for the natural slope, this factor is zero so $P6 = 0$ was used in the above formula.

Slope Stability Analysis

The slope stability is calculated using Slope Mass Rating (SMR; Romana 1993). This slope geomechanical classification provides a systematic approach for quantifying the adjustment factors, and for analyzing the failure susceptibility of rock slopes. The function used for the calculation of SMR is (Romana 1993):

$$SMR = RMR_b + (F1.F2.F3) + F4$$

Where F1 depends on parallelism between joints and slope face strikes; F2 refers to the joint dip angle in the planar mode of failure; F3 reflects the relationship between slope face and joint dip; and F4 is the excavation factor for the method of excavation.

RESULTS:

As elucidated at the outset of this paper, a comprehensive compilation of geotechnical data encompassing 39 slopes was undertaken. However, due to a significant proportion of these slopes undergoing treatment, their analysis might not yield precise outcomes. Consequently, a focused approach was adopted, concentrating on nine accessible sites exhibiting comparatively minimal or negligible treatment. These selected sites were then subjected to in-depth analysis. The ensuing sections present the outcomes of these analyses for each of the nine landslides, encompassing parameters such as the Basic Rock Mass Rating (RMR_b), the Slope Mass Rating (SMR), and failure indices.

Gul Rock Topple ($33^{\circ}16'0.67''N$, $75^{\circ}2'5.07''E$)

Situated in close proximity to the Gul village, this landslide is prominently visible along the southeastern-facing slopes. It poses a significant threat to the inhabitants of nearby villages, including Gul and Thatarka. Spanning across a ridge line oriented in a north-south direction near Thatarka village, this landslide area comprises alternating bands of thickly bedded grey sandstone and red claystone belonging to the Murree Formation. The crown of the landslide lies to the north of a small lake adjacent to Budhan village.

Notably, the sandstone beds in this region exhibit considerable variability in thickness, with the thickest beds measuring up to 5 meters, a substantial contrast to the relatively thinner siltstone and claystone beds, measuring around 2 meters and less than 1 meter respectively. The orientation of the bedding plane (S0) here is predominantly east-west, dipping at an angle of 30-50 degrees to the north. Additionally, two joint planes are evident: joint plane J1 exhibits a northeast-southwest strike and dips at 25-30 degrees northwest, while joint plane J2 has a northwest-southeast strike and a dipping angle of approximately 45 degrees northeast.

In close proximity, an old landslide has been observed, previously documented by Singh (2009), near the Gul village along the road leading to Sangaldhan. Here, the road has

experienced a shift of approximately 20 meters downwards. The sandstone in this region is extensively jointed, particularly pronounced near the toe of the slope ($J_v = 63$). Meanwhile, the crown of the landslide is predominantly veiled by inclined pine trees, an indication of ongoing creeping activity. Sizeable sandstone boulders have traversed the slope alongside a wet clay matrix, implying a wet to dripping moisture condition in the upslope areas.

Upon conducting a kinematic analysis of the area, the type of failure is determined to be a rock fall, with respective failure indices of 0.03 and 0.33 for wedge and topple failures. This interpretation aligns with the presence of south-dipping beds associated with wedge failure, while slopes characterized by steep angles are linked to toppling failure mechanisms (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Representation of kinematic data along the Gul road.

ANALYTICAL CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the findings of this study shed light on the prevalence of landslides within the Lesser Himalayan region, particularly in the Murree and Salkhala Formations. While the majority of landslides occur within these rock units, exceptions are reported in areas adjacent to

significant geological structures, often involving rocks from the Siwalik Formation. The occurrence of landslides is notably heightened during the monsoon season, although toe cutting emerges as a substantial contributor to landslide reactivation. Notably, regions with moderate elevations within the central part of the study area exhibit a higher frequency of landslides compared to areas of lower or higher elevations.

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An intriguing observation is that certain slopes, despite being assigned fair rock conditions based on the Rock Mass Rating (RMR) and Slope Mass Rating (SMR)

systems, do not accurately represent the actual site conditions. This underscores the need for improved evaluation techniques, particularly along the Lesser Himalaya.

Figure 2: A cross-sectional profile along the Study area (Index map shows the location of study area).

Figure 3: RMR and SMR contours along the study area

Furthermore, the specific case of the landslide near Gul village along the southeast-facing slopes was investigated in detail. This landslide poses a threat to the inhabitants of surrounding villages such as Gul and Thataka. It is situated amidst alternating bands of thick grey sandstone and red claystone from the Murree Formation, aligned along a ridge line extending north-south near Thataka village. The crown of this landslide lies northward of a small lake in proximity to Budhan village.

The sandstone beds at this site display significant variations in thickness, with the thickest reaching up to 5 meters, in stark contrast to the siltstone and claystone beds measuring around 2 meters and less than 1 meter respectively. Various planes are observable, including the bedding plane (S0) oriented almost east-west, dipping at 30-50 degrees to the north. Joint planes J1 and J2 exhibit different orientations and dipping angles.

An additional historical landslide, previously documented by Singh et al. (2013), is noted near the Gul village along the road leading to Sangaldhan. This location has experienced a shift of approximately 20 meters downward.

The sandstone in the area is heavily jointed near the toe, while the crown is covered with pine trees exhibiting creeping behaviour. Boulders of massive sandstone mixed with wet clay matrix have slid along the slope, indicating a wet to dripping moisture condition. Kinematic analysis classifies this area as a rock fall type of failure, featuring failure indices for wedge and topple failures.

In summation, this study provides a comprehensive understanding of landslide occurrences, characteristics, and underlying factors within the study area, offering insights that can contribute to effective mitigation and management strategies in similar geological contexts.

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